

Nina Thornhill and ABB Norway: A unique experience of long-term collaboration

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Abstract: An overview of Professor Nina Thornhill's impact on the university-industry collaboration from a genuine curiosity and long-term investment in industry collaboration.

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1. INTRODUCTION

What an amazing journey we have had together with Nina Thornhill. After earlier contacts, Nina first came to Norway on sabbatical in 2005 for six months to work on plant wide disturbance analysis.

We have all become well acquainted with Nina and are impressed by her capacity and continuous curiosity. Nina shows particularly three abilities, which describe her success. She is:

- Always well-prepared, humble, patient and a very good listener;
- Able to summarise and formulate clear actions, also from vague discussions;
- Consistently focusing on the long-term goal even though it may be challenging to recognise the right steps to get there.

It is quite unique to enjoy such a close collaboration with a professor over so many years, which has resulted in many collaborative papers and Ph.D. theses as well as the possibility to dive deep into new areas of relevance both from an academic point of view as well as being relevant for industry.

2. EU PROJECT COLLABORATION

We have participated in three collaborative EU projects where Imperial College of London with Nina as the project coordinator. These projects have all been within the Marie Skłodowska Curie networks:

- Real-Smart 2010-2014
- Energy SmartOps 2011-2015
- PRONTO 2016 – 2019

In the Real-Smart project, we particularly focused on electrical systems in large industrial sites. The EU program supported mobility, secondments and exchanges between the project partners aiming to

provide career development of researchers and building networks for initial training. We hosted two Ph.D. students from Imperial College, Inês Cecilio (2011) focusing on Causal Signal Analysis and Izzati Mohd Noor Nur (2013-2014) who worked on Demand Side Management for Load Reduction. In addition, two ABB employees went on secondment to Imperial College to work with Nina; Trond Haugen develop a cross university-industry strategy and roadmap for Process Power Management and Yuanyuan Ma worked on Time Synchronisation of Large Data Sets from Disparate Sources.

The Energy SmartOps project was an initial training network for Early Stage Researchers (ESR) who were encouraged to combine their research projects with a Ph.D. Energy SmartOps addressed the integrated control and operation of processes, rotating machinery and electrical equipment to achieve energy savings. David Romero was employed as our ESR. His research concerned Visualisation of Plant Dependencies.

The PRONTO project focuses on process network optimization for efficient and sustainable operation of Europe's process industries taking machinery condition and process performance into account. We have extensive collaboration with several ESRs and have hosted and supervised Marta Zagorowska and Francesco Borghesan together with Nina. This project is still ongoing and we have regular meetings with both Nina and the ESRs to provide support and supervision.

3. KNOWLEDGE TRANSFER

The education of students has been essential in our successful collaboration and competence build-up with Nina. During the years, Nina has attracted and

Figure 1. Nina together with Sara Budinis and Trond in the Carbon Capture Pilot Plant at Imperial College

supervised many highly qualified Ph.D. students and a good number of these, if not all of them, have either through EU programs or because of Nina's genuine interest in industrial applications had secondments or visits to ABB, many of these in Norway.

In addition to the ESRs within the EU programs, we have also hosted:

- Lamia Benabbas
- Waqas Ikram
- Nick Chen
- Ying Iván Xuan (2017, 2018 and 2019)

Together with Nina, we have explored and developed competence in known and new areas. One specific example that is worth to mention is the field of Power and Process. Based on Nina's extensive knowledge in process and process control combined with her curiosity to learn new things, we have worked on the interface between process and power for many years. Both of these areas are well-established, known and recognised. We have addressed the question of how these two fields influence each other to further improve system reliability.

We have been privileged to employ several of Nina's Ph.D. students over the years to ensure knowledge transfer from academia into the industry (Lamia, Waqas, Nick and David).

In addition, we have an extensive network with many of Nina's students, both M.Sc. students and Ph.D. students.

4. SUMMARY

Figure 2. Nina and Charlotte participating the PRONTO network meeting in Krakow, June 2019

The extended collaboration for almost 20 years has resulted in more than 20 collaborative papers, Ph.D. projects, secondments and countless constructive and innovative discussions. The projects and people mentioned in this article are just a subset of Nina's involvement with industry and academic colleagues. She is enthusiastic and easily engaged in the innovative environment, sees people and is both inclusive and listen to people. Many colleagues throughout the years have collaborated with Nina in one way or another. Therefore the list is long of those who have taken part in Nina's journey in ABB Norway.

A significant contribution is the work within Power for Process. During the years, we have realised that this area might be something more than just the interface between two well-establish disciplines, in fact it ought to be recognised as a new discipline. Several of the Ph.D. projects have addressed this discipline with strong academic results, which are tightly anchored in real industrial projects.

Figure 3. Nina with the PRONTO ESRs

Nina has certainly opened up a world of opportunities, which is unique for a university-industry collaboration. It is almost entirely due to her personal drive and determination. Nina is a pioneer in the way that she has collaborated with industry during her long sabbaticals with ABB, two of them in Norway (2005 and 2019) working within the Technology and Innovation team and with our customers.

We are very privileged that we have been on this unique journey together with Nina Thornhill and it is an honour that Nina has prioritised to work with us and our team. We will all miss, first and foremost, her presence, ideas, drive and discussions.

Finally, the process of writing this Festschrift has been very nice and we have smiled a lot while thinking back at episodes, discussions and situations that we have shared with Nina.